

EDAP+ TN on Quality Assessment of ICEYE X11, X12 and X13

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

ICEYE is an X-band SAR satellite constellation formed by many relatively small satellites, each one weighted approximately 120 kg [RD-1]. It is currently the world's largest SAR constellation with over 20 satellites launched since 2018, and at least another 20 planned to be launched during 2023-2024 [RD-2]. The constellation thus enables imaging of specified areas of interest multiple times a day, allowing quick tactical acquisitions as well as frequent revisit rates globally. The newer ICEYE satellites include improvements compared to the older ones.

The quality assessment described in this document is performed following the SAR specific EDAP+ assessment guidelines [RD-3], on the 2nd generation ICEYE satellites X11, X12 and X13. These satellites were launched on the 30th of June 2021, on board of the Falcon 9 Block 5 rocket of SpaceX. The quality assessment is divided into two main parts: Documentation review and an analysis of the test datasets. The document review in Chapter 2 includes the assessment of the documentation provided by ICEYE. The grading of these documents is given in columns 1-3 of the Summary Cal/Val Maturity Matrix (Figure 1-1) in section 1.3.1. Chapter 3 describes the data assessment performed by the EDAP+ team for the test data delivered by ICEYE from requested validation sites. A generic grading for the data assessment is given in the last column of the Summary Cal/Val Maturity Matrix (Figure 1-1), and a more specific grading for the different quality parameters is given in the Validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix (Figure 1-2). Similar assessments have been previously performed on ICEYE's X2-X7 1st generation satellites [RD-4, RD-5], for which the final reports are available in the European Space Agency (ESA) EDAP+ project web page.

The interactive documentation available online in the ICEYE webpages, and the calibration-validation documentation shared by ICEYE with the EDAP+ team (not publicly available) [RD-6], provided comprehensive information about the ICEYE data products and the internal validation activities performed by ICEYE. The online documentation corresponds to the traditional Product User Guide and ATBD. The documentation is continuously being updated, currently versions 5.0-5.2 are available. Older versions of the ICEYE documents in pdf-format [RD-7, RD-8] and a conference publication [RD-9] are also available online. In addition to the basic Level 1 SAR products, ICEYE offers higher level products and solutions in various topics, including flood monitoring, vessel detection, agriculture, ice chart mapping for sea navigation and oil spill detection. Documentation describing these analyses can be accessed upon registration through ICEYE's website.

All necessary and relevant details on the ICEYE products are publicly available in the online product documentation, previous versions of product documentation [RD-7, RD-8] and in a conference publication [RD-9]. The data is provided to the user in standard file formats, easily read and understood, such as HDF5, GeoTIFF and XML. The data can be easily accessed and processed also with the publicly available SNAP toolbox distributed by ESA. Data order and delivery to the customer was smooth due to well written and clear instructions regarding the FTP delivery procedures. Product metadata includes the relevant flags with the necessary information on the data products. Ancillary data used in product generation relevant for SAR are also specified in the metadata or product documentation. All relevant characteristics of the SAR sensor system and SAR system geometry are stated in the documentation and/or in the product metadata, but documentation about pre-flight calibration activities is minimal. The metrological traceability of the ICEYE products is not documented.

A general description of the post-launch radiometric and geometric calibration methods and activities, as well as the uncertainty characterization and quality assessment performed internally by ICEYE, is given in the online product documentation. A more detailed description of these, specifically for the X11-X13 satellites, is given in a document provided to the EDAP+ team [RD-6]. All relevant uncertainty values for SAR are thus provided, such as the spatial resolution, ISLR (Integrated Side Lobe Ratio), PSLR (Peak Side Lobe Ratio), NESZ (Noise Equivalent Sigma Zero) and geolocation accuracy. The given uncertainty values are based on analyses of several datasets. Single uncertainty values for each imaging mode are provided in the ICEYE web site and in the online interactive documentation, while more detailed results for X11-X13 are presented in RD-6. Pixel-wise uncertainty is not provided. The calibration algorithm and the geometric processing of

the data products are well documented in the online documentation and in the additional document RD-6 provided to EDAP+ team.

An independent assessment of the essential quality parameters for SAR was performed by the EDAP+ team, using representative datasets acquired with ICEYE's X11-X13 satellites. Data were collected from various test sites enabling a comprehensive assessment of the most relevant SAR quality parameters, such as the spatial resolution, PSLR, ISLR, geolocation accuracy, equivalent number of looks (ENL), NESZ, antenna elevation pattern (AEP), and radiometric stability. The measured quality parameters in our analyses were compared with the corresponding values stated in ICEYE's documentation. The validation was performed using the SAR Quality Toolbox (SQT) dedicated to the assessment of SAR data quality (<https://www.aresys.it/end-to-end-simulation/>), developed by Aresys. Processing was also tested with the SNAP toolbox. The evaluated test datasets include Single Look Complex (SLC) products of the Strip and Spot imaging modes, previously known as Stripmap (SM) and Spotlight High Resolution (SLH) modes, respectively. All ICEYE data are in VV-polarization (single-polarization), with incidence angles ranging between 15 and 35 degrees. There were few scenes delivered by ICEYE where the radiometric quality was low, and several scenes where the localization error was found large. Following a request from the EDAP+ team, these scenes were reprocessed by ICEYE, and their quality was usually considerably improved.

The measured quality parameters assessed in the IRF analysis performed over the corner reflector (CR) sites were generally in line with the values provided by ICEYE. The spatial resolution was usually similar or even better than the provided values. The PSLR and ISLR were typically within the expected range, and similar to the results presented by ICEYE in RD-6. Compared to other X-band SAR data providers, the ICEYE products have generally higher spatial resolution, but also relatively high side lobes. This is because no smoothing window function (e.g. Taylor, Hanning, Hamming or Kaiser) is applied by ICEYE during data processing. The measured localization errors in azimuth and slant range directions were in accordance with the values provided by ICEYE, but if projected from slant to ground range, the errors were typically larger than the stated values.

The measured NESZ was typically higher (worse) than the values provided in the ICEYE documentation. However, this is related to an overestimation by the SQT due to differences in the methodology used in the NESZ estimation compared to the one used by ICEYE. Also, finding an ideal target with very low backscatter was challenging, as the highest (shallowest) available incidence angle for ICEYE is only 30° for Strip and 35° for Spot acquisition modes. The ENL in the homogenous Glacier and Desert targets was very close to the ideal value of 1 for SLC data, indicating correct radiometric processing of the data. The AEP correction performed by the data provider for the Spot data was successful. For the Strip imaging mode, in which the AEP correction is more challenging due to the larger variation in the antenna elevation, there were more distinct differences between the analysed satellites. AEP correction of X11 had the best performance, with relatively flat gamma nought backscatter (γ^0) range profiles and no clear decreasing or increasing trends from near to far range. X12 had the weakest performance, with clear increasing or decreasing trends from near to far range, and X13 showed similar behaviour than X12, but with somewhat smaller biases. The AEP correction was generally more successful for the scenes acquired at ~30° incidence angle, compared to the ones acquired at ~20° incidence angle. The radiometric stability of the observations over the Amazonas Rainforest was in line with the radiometric accuracy stated by ICEYE, with observed deviations of usually less than 0.5 dB from the most typically measured backscatter level. The higher resolution Spot imaging mode showed slightly better stability than the Strip data, which may be related to the better AEP correction for Spot. A significant improvement in the radiometric stability can be seen when comparing these results with the ones derived for the 1st generation ICEYE satellites [RD-5].

The ICEYE data were successfully processed in the publicly available SNAP toolbox, version 9.0. The tested processing steps included image subset, calibration, georeferencing including terrain correction, and speckle filtering. Based on our evaluation results and in light of the quality values provided by ICEYE, we conclude that the quality of X11-X13 satellites is generally in a good agreement with the values stated by ICEYE. We found a notable improvement compared to the 1st generation X2-X7 ICEYE satellites concerning AEP correction and radiometric stability.

1.1 References

The following is a list of reference documents with a direct bearing on the content of this proposal. Where referenced in the text, these are identified as [RD-n], where 'n' is the number in the list below:

RD-1. ICEYE brochure Q2 2023: Buy ICEYE SAR Satellites Rapidly Delivered. Available online:
https://www.iceye.com/hubfs/_DATA_AND_MISSIONS/Missions_Brochure_ICEYE.pdf (06/2023)

RD-2. ICEYE brochure Q2 2023: A Revolution in Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) Data Earth Observation. Available online:
https://www.iceye.com/hubfs/Downloadables/SAR_Data_Brochure_ICEYE.pdf (06/2023)

RD-3. EDAP Best Practice Guidelines, EDAP.REP.001, v1.2, September 2019.

RD-4. ICEYE X2 Quality Assessment Summary, EDAP report. Available online:
<https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/activities/edap/sar-missions> (07/2023)

RD-5. ICEYE X4, X6 and X7 Quality Assessment Summary, EDAP report. Available online:
<https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/activities/edap/sar-missions> (07/2023)

RD-6. SAR Calibration and Performance Verification for X11-X13 satellites, 2023, ICEYE

RD-7. SAR Product Guide, Version 3.0. released in 01.05.2020, ICEYE

RD-8. Data Calibration and Validation, version 1.0, released 22/6/2020, ICEYE

RD-9. V. Ignatenko, P. Laurila, A. Radius, L. Lamentowski, O. Antropov and D. Muff, "ICEYE Microsatellite SAR Constellation Status Update: Evaluation of First Commercial Imaging Modes," *IGARSS 2020 - 2020 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, Waikoloa, HI, USA, 2020, pp. 3581-3584, doi: 10.1109/IGARSS39084.2020.9324531.

RD-10. M. C. Garthwaite, M. Hazelwood, S. Nancarrow, A. Hislop & J. H. Dawson (2015) A regional geodetic network to monitor ground surface response to resource extraction in the northern Surat Basin, Queensland, *Australian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 62:4, 469-477, DOI: 10.1080/08120099.2015.1040073

1.2 Glossary

The following acronyms and abbreviations have been used in this Report.

AEP	Antenna Elevation Pattern
ALE	Absolute Localization Error
ATBD	Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document
CR	Corner Reflector
EDAP	Earthnet Data Assessment Project

ENL	Equivalent Number Looks
ESA	European Space Agency
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GRD	Ground Range Detected
ISLR	Integrated Side Lobe Ratio
NESZ	Noise Equivalent Sigma Zero
PSLR	Peak Side Lobe Ratio
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SLC	Single Look Complex
SLH	SpotLight High resolution
SM	StripMap
SNAP	SeNtinel Application Platform
SQT	SAR Quality Toolbox

1.3 Cal/Val Maturity Matrices

1.3.1 Summary Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

Data Provider Documentation Review			Validation Summary	Key
Product Information	Metrology	Product Generation		Not Assessed
Product Details	Sensor Calibration & Characterisation	Measurement Validation Method	Not Assessable	
Availability & Accessibility	Geometric Calibration & Characterisation	Basic		
Product Format, Flags & Metadata	Metrological Traceability Documentation	Mission-Specific Processing	Geometric Validation Method	Good
User Documentation	Excellent			
	Ancillary Data			Not Public

Figure 1-1: Summary Cal/Val Maturity Matrix for the ICEYE X11-X13 satellites.

1.3.2 Validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

FMI Detailed Validation			
Measurement		Geometric	
NESZ Method	NESZ Results Compliance		
ENL Method	ENL Results Compliance	Spatial Resolution Method	Spatial Resolution Results Compliance
AEP Method	AEP Results Compliance		
Stability Method	Stability Results Compliance	ISLR Method	ISLR Results Compliance

Key
Not Assessed
Not Assessable
Basic
Good
Excellent
Ideal
Not Public

Figure 1-2: Validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix for the ICEYE X11-X13 satellites.

2. DATA PROVIDER DOCUMENTATION REVIEW

2.1 Product Information

Product Details	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<i>All necessary product details are provided in the online product documentation, older versions of documents in pdf-format, and/or in a conference publication [RD-9]. Radiometric accuracy is provided only in the older documentation and the conference publication.</i>
Product Name	<i>ICEYE_[sat. number]_[PL]_[im.mode]_[id]_YYYYMMDDTHHmss, where [sat. number] is the number of the ICEYE satellite; X4-X7. [PL] is the processing level of the product; SLC or GRD. [im. mode] is the imaging mode; SC for ScanSAR, SM for Stripmap, SL and SLH for Spotlight High. [id] is a seven-digit product identification number. YYYYMMDD and HHmss are the acquisition start date and time.</i>
Sensor Name	<i>X11, X12 and X13 were evaluated</i>
Sensor Type	<i>X-band SAR, 2nd generation</i>
Mission Type	<i>Constellation – 3 satellites out of the constellation are evaluated</i>
Mission Orbit	<i>Sun Synchronous Polar Orbit</i>
Product Version Number	<i>The evaluated products are of processor versions 1.79- 1.90</i>
Product ID	<i>A number with seven digits individual for each product</i>
Processing level of product	<i>Level 1 SLC products were evaluated</i>
Measured Quantity Name	<i>Radar Backscatter</i>
Measured Quantity Units	<i>dB</i>
Stated Measurement Quality	<i>Absolute radiometric accuracy, namely the RMSE between measured and true RCS, is estimated < 2 dB. Relative radiometric accuracy, namely the standard deviation of the radiometric error of known targets within one data take, is estimated < 1 dB.</i>
Spatial Resolution	<i>Spot, Strip and Scan acquisition modes are offered. The spatial resolution (range X azimuth) for each mode is: Scan: 15 x 15 (GRD) Strip: 0.5-2.5 x 3 (SLC) Spot: 0.5 x 0.25 (SLC)</i>
Spatial Coverage	<i>Size of one standard scene (swath width x length) Scan: 100 x 100 Strip: 30 x 50 Spot: 5 x 5</i>
Temporal Resolution	<i>Daily repeat pass for selected targets (not yet global)</i>
Temporal Coverage	<i>Constellation mean revisit time at the equator is 20 hours. Constellation mean time to access at equator is 12 hours.</i>
Point of Contact	<i>customer@iceye.com</i>

Product locator (DOI/URL)	NA
Conditions for access and use	<i>Data were provided under specific agreement for utilization within the EDAP+ framework.</i>
Limitations on public access	<i>Data not publicly accessible</i>
Product Abstract	NA

Availability & Accessibility	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<i>Most of the Fair principles met, except: Metadata and data include qualified references to other (meta)data.</i>
Compliant with FAIR principles	<i>Mostly yes</i>
Data Management Plan	<i>Standard orders are submitted by filling out a Standard Order Form with required information on requested datasets, via email for existing users and via sending an email to the customer service for new customers. Custom orders with a higher level of flexibility are initiated by submitting a Custom Order Form via the email for existing customers, and by contacting the ICEYE sales team through ICEYE website for new customers. Archive imagery orders can be submitted via email. Access to the public archive of ICEYE radar preview imagery is possible after registration. The available archive scenes can be previewed e.g. in Google Earth, QGIS or other common GIS-software.</i>
Availability Status	<i>Standard orders are delivered via SFTP server to the customer within 12 hours after the data is acquired. Faster delivery of only a few hours is possible for urgent requests. Archive scenes are delivered up to 12 hours after an order is received. It is possible to use free software (e.g. SNAP) for data processing and analysis.</i>

Product Format	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<i>Data provided in standard file formats. Relevant flags included, such as flags indicating if antenna elevation pattern and free space loss compensation, and windowing function were applied. Metadata includes all necessary information on the data products.</i>
Product File Format	<i>HDF5 and XML for SLC data GeoTIFF and XML for GRD data PNG and KML for quicklook images</i>
Metadata Conventions	<i>HDF, XML</i>
Analysis Ready Data?	<i>No</i>

User Documentation		
Grade: Excellent		
Justification	<p>An online interactive product documentation is provided in the ICEYE webpages. This includes comprehensive information about the products, corresponding to the traditional Product User Guide and ATBD. Downloadable product documentation (pdf-versions) include the "SAR data brochure" and "Missions Brochure", which provide basic information on the data products and quality, and older versions of documentation. The online documentation is continuously being updated, currently versions 5.0-5.2 available.</p>	
<i>Document</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>QA4ECV Compliant</i>
Product User Guide	ICEYE online product documentation	no
ATBD	ICEYE online product documentation	no

2.2 Metrology

Sensor Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<i>All relevant characteristics of the SAR sensor system are stated in the documentation and/or in the product metadata. Documentation about pre-flight calibration activities is minimal. A general description of the post-launch radiometric (sensor) calibration methods and activities is given in the online product documentation. A more detailed description of the calibration and validation activities for the X11-X13 satellites is given in RD-6. The radiometric calibration was performed using homogeneous targets and point targets. It included e.g. antenna elevation beam calibration and calibration coefficient calculation. Calibration against homogeneous targets was initially performed over Amazon rainforest, and a validation of the calibration parameters was done using Congo rainforest data. The corner reflectors in Rosamond JPL site were used in the radiometric calibration against point targets. The calibration parameters were derived through an analysis of many images. Routine and ongoing validation activities are planned for the operational ICEYE satellites.</i>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICEYE online product documentation • RD-6

Geometric Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<i>All relevant characteristics of the SAR system geometry are stated in the documentation and/or in the product metadata. Documentation about pre-flight geometric calibration activities is minimal. A general description of the post-launch geometric calibration methods and activities is given in the online product documentation. A more detailed description of the calibration and validation activities for the X11-X13 satellites is given in RD-6. The geometric calibration and verification was performed using point target calibration sites around the world, specifically the NASA JPL corner reflector array in Rosamond, California. The calibration parameters were evaluated through an analysis of many images. Routine and ongoing validation activities are planned for the operational ICEYE satellites.</i>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICEYE online product documentation • RD-6

Metrological Traceability Documentation	
Grade: Not Assessable	
Justification	<i>Metrological traceability not documented</i>
References	NA

Uncertainty Characterisation	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<p><i>The methods and the results of the uncertainty characterization performed internally by ICEYE are well documented. A more general description of the methods and results of the uncertainty characterisation and quality assessment is provided in the online documentation, while a more detailed description concerning the X11-X13 satellites was provided in RD-6. The uncertainty characterisation includes the relevant quality indicators for SAR, such as an IRF analyses for the assessment of spatial resolution, side lobes and localization error, as well as radiometric validation, including NESZ, radiometric accuracy, AEP,</i></p> <p><i>All relevant uncertainty values for SAR are thus provided. The given uncertainty values are based on analyses of several datasets. Single uncertainty values for each imaging mode are provided in the ICEYE web site and in the online interactive documentation, while more detailed results for X11-X13 are presented in RD-6. Pixel-wise uncertainty is not provided. Radiometric accuracy is provided only in the old versions of the product documentation.</i></p>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICEYE online product documentation • RD-6 • RD-7 • RD-9

Ancillary Data	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<p><i>Ancillary data used in product generation relevant for SAR are specified in the metadata or product documentation, such as the digital elevation model used, not on a per product basis.</i></p>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICEYE online product documentation

2.3 Product Generation

Calibration Algorithm	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<i>Calibration algorithm well documented. The SAR processor compensates for the effects of range spread loss, elevation antenna pattern, different azimuth and range bandwidths, and sensor settings variations (receiver gain, transmit power, duty cycle). Further calibration and validation activities are routinely performed for the ICEYE satellites [RD-6, RD-8]. Information about the performed calibration is provided in the metadata per product, such as the amplification factors for antenna elevation and free space loss compensation.</i>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICEYE online product documentation • RD-6 • RD-8

Geometric Processing	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<i>The geometric processing is well documented and all relevant calibration parameters are provided. In azimuth image pixels are always focused to the zero-Doppler. In range the processor applies path length corrections (typically on the order of a couple of metres) using well established models. An RPC model has been implemented for the determination of precise pixel locations. Timing corrections are applied to satellite internal clocks by periodically synchronising with GNSS. The satellite position and velocity state vectors are refined after the imaging operation using downlinked telemetry and attitude data. For amplitude scenes, a conversion from Beta Nought to Sigma Nought is applied using the incidence angle calculated from the ellipsoid model. The geolocation accuracy of the satellites is routinely verified by collecting and analysing images over ground-surveyed calibration sites containing calibration point targets such as trihedral corner reflectors.</i>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICEYE online product documentation • RD-6 • RD-8

Mission-Specific Processing	
Grade: Not Assessable	
Justification	<i>Additional processing steps are not documented.</i>
Reference	NA

3. DETAILED VALIDATION – MEASUREMENT

This chapter describes the assessment of the radiometric quality parameters performed by the EDAP+ team over the homogeneous test areas, using test datasets of the X11, X12 and X13 satellites. These quality parameters include the Noise Equivalent Sigma Zero (NESZ), Equivalent Number of Looks (ENL), Antenna Elevation Pattern (AEP) and radiometric stability. The validation of the IRF quality parameters is presented in Chapter 4.

3.1 Introduction

For evaluating the radiometric quality, data from homogeneous and low backscatter areas were collected. Rainforests are considered a stable and homogeneous target with relatively low dependency of the measured backscatter on imaging angle, due to the influence of the dense forest canopies. Therefore, rainforests are ideal for assessing the calibration with respect to the antenna elevation angle, namely AEP, and the radiometric stability between different scenes. Glaciers are also considered homogeneous targets for SAR, and they are used in our analysis for the assessment of the ENL. In previous EDAP assessments of X-band SAR data, glaciers were found more suitable for assessing the ENL than rainforests, most likely because concerning the relatively high spatial resolution X-band measurements, rainforests are not as homogeneous as glaciers.

The Ocean Doldrums zone as well as smooth desert surfaces cause low backscatter, due to specular reflection of the radar signal on the smooth surfaces and high penetration in the dry desert sand. Scenes from the low backscatter targets of Atlantic Doldrums and Sahara Desert are used in our analysis to assess the NESZ. The Sahara images are also used for assessing the ENL, because of the chosen homogeneous desert surfaces. Table 1 lists the test areas used for the radiometric evaluation, and which quality parameters were assessed in each area.

Table 1: The radiometric quality parameters assessed for each test area.

Test Area	NESZ	ENL	AEP	Stability
Rainforest			X	X
Glacier		X		
Doldrums	X			
Desert	X	X		

The SAR Quality Toolbox developed by Aresys was used for assessing the above-mentioned quality metrics. The measured quality values were evaluated by comparing them with the corresponding quality values provided by ICEYE in the publicly available documentation and in the additional documentation not publicly available but provided by ICEYE to the EDAP+ assessment team. The evaluation results are considered good if the measured quality parameters are better or similar than the values provided by ICEYE. On the contrary, the quality is considered weak if the measured quality parameters are worse than the provided values in the documents. In case there were not any defined values for a certain quality parameter in the ICEYE documentation, the grading was decided based on commonly known values typical to X-band SAR sensors.

Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3 list the test areas, imaging modes, product ID numbers, acquisition dates, average incidence angles, and processor version numbers of the ICEYE scenes used by the evaluation team for assessment purposes within the EDAP+ activity, for X11, X12 and X13 satellites, respectively.

Table 2: X11 data products included in the assessment of the radiometric quality parameters, provided by ICEYE to the EDAP+ team.

Test Area	Imaging mode	ID number	Date	Incidence Angle	Processor version	
Low backscatter water or desert	Strip	1803339	2023-01-27	30.5	1.80	
		1817737	2023-02-01	26.8	1.80	
		1839745	2023-02-01	28.3	1.80	
		1839746	2023-02-02	27.9	1.80	
		1839747	2023-02-02	29.7	1.80	
	Spot	1801594	2023-01-20	29.6	1.79	
		1801595	2023-01-21	29.6	1.79	
		1801596	2023-01-21	29.8	1.79	
		1801597	2023-01-22	29.5	1.80	
		1801598	2023-01-22	29.8	1.80	
	Desert, Sahara	Strip	1801689	2023-01-22	29.3	1.79
			1801819	2023-01-23	29.9	1.80
Spot		1803341	2023-01-25	29.2	1.80	
		1803342	2023-01-26	30.3	1.80	
Homogeneous areas	Strip	1801126	2023-01-19	29.5	1.79	
		1801127	2023-01-21	29.5	1.79	
		1801128	2023-01-19	29.5	1.79	
		1803330	2023-01-24	20.2	1.80	
		1803331	2023-01-25	20.0	1.80	
		1803332	2023-01-24	20.3	1.80	
	Spot	1803334	2023-01-26	21.5	1.80	
		1803337	2023-01-29	32.5	1.80	
		1812896	2023-01-29	22.7	1.80	
		1812898	2023-01-30	27.5	1.80	
		1817733	2023-01-30	29.3	1.80	
		1843961	2023-02-04	21.0	1.80	
	Glacier, Greenland	Strip	1801357	2023-01-20	20.1	1.79
			1801401	2023-01-21	30.2	1.79
		Spot	1801319	2023-01-19	20.9	1.79
		1801466	2023-01-22	29.9	1.80	

Table 3: X12 data products included in the assessment of the radiometric quality parameters, provided by ICEYE to the EDAP+ team.

Test Area	Imaging mode	ID number	Date	Incidence angle	Processor version
Low backscatter water or desert	Strip	1801642	2023-01-27	28.8	1.80
		1805280	2023-01-27	30.4	1.80
		1805281	2023-01-28	30.8	1.80
		1839748	2023-02-01	28.2	1.80
		1839749	2023-02-01	28.4	1.80
	Spot	1801599	2023-01-20	29.8	1.79
		1801600	2023-01-21	29.7	1.79
		1801601	2023-01-21	29.6	1.79
		1801602	2023-01-21	29.9	1.79
		1801603	2023-01-22	29.7	1.79
		1801690	2023-01-21	29.7	1.79
	Desert, Sahara	Strip	1801691	2023-01-22	29.6
1801740			2023-01-23	31.5	1.80
Spot		1821541	2023-02-02	29.6	1.80
		1801130	2023-01-19	29.5	1.79
Homogeneous areas	Strip	1801202	2023-01-23	20.2	1.80
		1801203	2023-01-24	20.9	1.80
		1801204	2023-01-23	21.2	1.80
		1874303	2023-02-12	29.8	1.80
		1883410	2023-02-18	28.7	1.80
		1801223	2023-01-26	21.7	1.80
	Spot	1817734	2023-02-01	32.5	1.80
		1817735	2023-01-31	33.1	1.80

			1817736	2023-01-31	33.2	1.80	
			1835808	2023-02-03	21.2	1.80	
			1843912	2023-02-04	22.4	1.80	
	Glacier, Greenland	Strip		1801358	2023-01-20	19.9	1.79
				1801402	2023-01-21	30.1	1.79
		Spot		1801320	2023-01-19	21.0	1.79
			1801467	2023-01-22	29.8	1.79	

Table 4: X13 data products included in the assessment of the radiometric quality parameters, provided by ICEYE to the EDAP+ team.

Test Area	Imaging mode	ID number	Date	Incidence angle	Processor version	
Low backscatter water or desert	Strip	1805463	2023-01-27	29.7	1.80	
		1805464	2023-01-28	29.5	1.80	
		1813155	2023-01-29	29.8	1.80	
		1816892	2023-01-31	30.1	1.80	
		1817738	2023-02-01	28.7	1.80	
	Spot	1801604	2023-01-20	29.7	1.79	
		1801605	2023-01-20	29.7	1.79	
		1801606	2023-01-21	29.7	1.79	
		1801607	2023-01-22	29.7	1.79	
		1801608	2023-01-22	29.7	1.80	
	Desert, Sahara	Strip	1801692	2023-01-22	29.7	1.80
			1801820	2023-01-24	29.6	1.80
		Spot	1801741	2023-01-26	31.9	1.80
			1801742	2023-01-23	31.5	1.80
Homogeneous areas	Strip	1801132	2023-01-20	29.5	1.79	
		1801134	2023-01-19	29.6	1.79	
		1801205	2023-01-25	19.8	1.80	
		1801206	2023-01-26	19.9	1.80	
		1801207	2023-01-25	20.7	1.80	
		1876892	2023-02-18	25.7	1.80	
	Spot	1801226	2023-01-26	21.0	1.80	
		1803237	2023-01-27	21.0	1.80	
		1807781	2023-01-29	29.6	1.80	
		1813153	2023-01-30	30.6	1.80	
		1813154	2023-01-29	31.1	1.80	
		1870064	2023-02-11	20.1	1.80	
	Glacier, Greenland	Strip	1801359	2023-01-20	20.2	1.79
			1801403	2023-01-21	30.3	1.79
		Spot	1801321	2023-01-19	21.2	1.79
		1801468	2023-01-22	29.8	1.80	

3.2 Equivalent Number of Looks (ENL)

The equivalent number of looks (ENL) indicates the degree of averaging applied to the SAR measurements during data generation and postprocessing. Hence, for multilook (averaged) images, such as the GRD data products, the ENL should be the number of observations used for calculating one representative backscatter value, while for single look images, such as the SLC data product, the ENL should be one.

3.2.1 Method

The ENL analysis is typically performed over natural distributed homogeneous targets. In this analysis the test areas used for the assessment were in the Greenland Glacier and Western Sahara Desert. All test data sets were SLC products, meaning that the number of looks is one. Therefore, the measured ENL values should be close to one. Traditionally the ENL has been assessed using

data from rainforests as well. However, in previous assessments of X-band SAR data we found, that the ENL of rainforests is typically notably below the ideal value of one for SLC data. This happens most likely because rainforests are not homogeneous enough regarding high resolution X-band SAR. In the current analysis of the X11-X13 satellites, the ENL over rainforest was also notably lower than one, namely around 0.6 for Strip and Spot alike. The analysis was performed using the SQT software, by manually selecting five homogeneous sub-areas over the scene and calculating the ENL over them. Figure 3 presents an example of a selection of the sub-areas for the ENL calculation, from the Spot scene 1801319 acquired over Greenland.

Figure 3: An example illustrating the selection of five sub-areas for the calculation of ENL, from the Spot scene 1801319 over Greenland.

3.2.2 Results Compliance

Table 5 and Table 6 show the median and the std of the measured ENL in Glacier and Desert, respectively.

Table 5: ENL results for the Greenland Glacier.

Satellite	Imaging mode	Scene ID	Median	Std
X11	Strip	1801357	0.991	0.001
		1801401	0.997	0.001
	Spot	1801319	0.988	0.002
		1801466	0.988	0.008
X12	Strip	1801358	0.997	0.001
		1801402	0.996	0.002
	Spot	1801320	0.989	0.005
		1801467	0.993	0.006
X13	Strip	1801359	0.980	0.006
		1801403	0.996	0.001
	Spot	1801321	0.959	0.005
		1801468	0.992	0.006

Table 6: ENL results for the Sahara Desert.

Satellite	Imaging mode	Scene ID	Median	Std
X11	Strip	1801689	0.955	0.016
		1801819	0.835	0.042
	Spot	1803341	0.427	0.294

		1803342	0.987	0.032
X12	Strip	1801690	0.987	0.014
		1801691	0.986	0.006
	Spot	1801740	0.994	0.012
		1821541	0.975	0.044
X13	Strip	1801692	0.983	0.017
		1801820	0.848	0.038
	Spot	1801741	0.988	0.010
		1801742	0.981	0.003

The measured ENL for the analysed ICEYE data from the Glacier and Desert sites was usually very close to the ideal value of ENL=1. For the Glacier, the maximum deviation from 1 was up to 0.2, except for one X13 Spot image showing 0.959. For the Desert, the deviation from 1 was usually similar than in Glacier, but with more exceptions showing smaller values ranging between 0.427 and 0.975. The exceptionally low values were most likely caused by inhomogeneities of the terrain due to desert fringes or rocks in the imaged areas. Hence, based on the ENL analysis over the Glaciers and the Desert sites, the results show correct radiometric signatures of the ICEYE SLC data.

3.3 Antenna Elevation Pattern (AEP)

The observed SAR backscatter needs to be corrected for changes caused by the antenna elevation angle in the range direction. A pre-defined antenna elevation pattern (AEP) is used by the data provider for compensating the contribution of the elevation angle to the measured gain. In this section we assessed whether the AEP correction was applied correctly on the data.

3.3.1 Method

The images were analysed by averaging the backscatter in azimuth direction and extracting range profiles of the averaged backscatter in slant range time units at five different points along the azimuth direction, as indicated by the narrow red boxes of Figure 4. The backscatter profiles were then normalized by the inverse of the average measured backscatter, and a second-order polynomial was fitted to the profiles. The analysis was performed on the Rainforest scenes, where the noise component can be considered negligible (very low) compared to the target backscatter level. Gamma nought (γ^0) backscatter was chosen because it is independent of the incidence angle with the ground surface. Ideally, the normalized γ^0 range profiles should be horizontal, with a value of zero dB all along the x-axis.

Figure 4: Illustration of the AEP assessment method with the X12 Strip image 1801203 from the Amazonas Rainforest in the background. Gamma nought (γ^0) backscatter profiles in range direction were extracted at five different points along the azimuth direction, marked with red boxes in the image. The backscatter was averaged in azimuth direction for deriving a range profile line.

3.3.2 Results Compliance

The figures below (Figure 5 - Figure 10) show the normalized antenna pattern with respect to the slant range time, extracted from the analysed SAR images. Range profiles of the X11 Spot and Strip data are shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6, respectively. Similarly, the profiles of X12 Spot and Strip data are shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8, and the profiles of X13 Spot and Strip in Figure 9 and Figure 10, respectively. In all these figures, plots in the first row are from the three scenes acquired with $\sim 20^\circ$ incidence angle, and the three plots in the second row are from the scenes with $\sim 30^\circ$ incidence angle.

Figure 5: AEP profiles of X11 Spot scenes from the Amazonas. Acquisitions having $\sim 20^\circ$ incidence angle are shown in the upper row and acquisitions with $\sim 30^\circ$ in the lower row.

Figure 6: AEP profiles of X11 Strip scenes from the Amazonas. Acquisitions having $\sim 20^\circ$ incidence angle are shown in the upper row and acquisitions with $\sim 30^\circ$ in the lower row.

Figure 7: AEP profiles of X12 Spot scenes from the Amazonas. Acquisitions having $\sim 20^\circ$ incidence angle are shown in the upper row and acquisitions with $\sim 30^\circ$ in the lower row.

Figure 8: AEP profiles of X12 Strip scenes from the Amazonas. Acquisitions having $\sim 20^\circ$ incidence angle are shown in the upper row and acquisitions with $\sim 30^\circ$ in the lower row.

Figure 9: AEP profiles of X13 Spot scenes from the Amazonas. Acquisitions having $\sim 20^\circ$ incidence angle are shown in the upper row and acquisitions with $\sim 30^\circ$ in the lower row.

Figure 10: AEP profiles of X13 Strip scenes from the Amazonas. Acquisitions having $\sim 20^\circ$ incidence angle are shown in the upper row and acquisitions with $\sim 30^\circ$ in the lower row.

Generally, the AEP correction performed by the data provider was more successful for the Spot imaging mode than for the Strip mode. This is expected, as the antenna elevation varies more in the wider Strip images, thus making it harder to compensate for the effect of the elevation angle. Also, the correction was generally more successful for the scenes acquired at the shallower, around 30° , incidence angle, compared to the $\sim 20^\circ$ incidence angle scenes. For the Spot scenes with the shallower $\sim 30^\circ$ incidence angle, the bias from the zero-line was always less than 0.5 dB, meaning good AEP correction along the whole elevation range. For the steeper incidence angle Spot scenes, the bias was usually below 0.5, but around 1 dB for one Spot scene of X12.

The differences in the AEP correction performances between the assessed satellites were more distinct in the Strip scenes, where the AEP correction is more challenging. AEP correction of X11 had the best performance, with relatively small biases from the zero-line, and sometimes a parabolic shape of the profiles with no clear decreasing or increasing trends from the near to the far range. X12 had the weakest performance, with relatively large biases of up to 2 dB for the $\sim 20^\circ$ scenes and 1 dB for the $\sim 30^\circ$ scenes, and with clear increasing or decreasing trends of 1-2 dB from the near to far range, in addition to a parabolic shape of the profiles. X13 show similar behaviour than X12, but with somewhat smaller biases compared to the X12 profiles. The parabolic shape of the profiles may be caused by image speckle effects, thus it is not necessarily related to the AEP correction performance. However, the increasing or decreasing trends between near and far range are most likely related of the changing antenna elevation angle.

The AEP correction can be therefore considered successful for the Spot data and good for the X11 Strip data. Somewhat weaker AEP correction performances were found for the X13 and X12 Strip data. When comparing with the ICEYE satellites of the older generation assessed in RD-4 and RD-5, the AEP analysis of X11-X13 performed here indicate notable improvement in the AEP correction performances compared to the older generations for both Spot and Strip imaging modes.

3.4 Noise Equivalent Sigma Zero (NESZ)

One of the most essential quality indicators in SAR is the noise equivalent sigma zero (NESZ), showing the contribution of noise in the observed backscatter. Weaker NESZ is an indication of higher quality SAR data, because targets with relatively low backscatter can be identified with less noise disturbance. The NESZ is typically assessed in calm water surfaces or dry and smooth desert areas due to their low backscatter.

3.4.1 Method

The NESZ is assessed here with images acquired over the Atlantic Doldrums zone at winter (January), and over smooth desert surfaces in Western Sahara (Figure 11). To minimize the observed backscatter, data with the shallowest (highest) possible incidence angle were chosen, namely around 30 degrees incidence angle. Data are analysed with the SQT by manually extracting and plotting radiometric profiles of the sigma nought (σ^0) backscatter in range direction from low backscatter areas. The range profiles are calculated at five different points along the azimuth direction, in a similar manner than in the AEP analysis (Figure 4), and the representative NESZ is considered the average σ^0 at the minimum of these profiles along the range direction. Since there may be some residual backscatter even in the selected relatively low backscatter areas, the minimum of the range profile graph showing the lowest backscatter can be considered the NESZ value, assuming that the contribution of the target itself to the observed backscatter power is negligible. Figure 12 shows an example of a range profile extracted from the Strip scene 1805280 over the Atlantic Doldrums.

Figure 11: The test areas of Atlantic Doldrums and Western Sahara that were used for assessing the NESZ, marked with red polygons over a Google Earth view.

Figure 12: A range profile of the Strip scene 1805280 from the Doldrums used for NESZ calculation.

3.4.2 Results Compliance

Table 7 shows the NESZ values of the data products provided in the ICEYE documentation. Table 8, Table 9 and Table 10 list the measured NESZ values for the X11, X12 and X13 data, respectively. As said, the values in the tables are the lowest calculated average values of the radiometric profiles.

Table 7: The NESZ values (dB) provided in the ICEYE documentation.

Imaging mode	NESZ [dB]
SM	- 21.5 ... -20
SLH	-18 ... -15

Table 8. NESZ of the X11 scenes for the Atlantic Doldrums and Sahara Desert.

Imaging mode	Area	Image ID	NESZ (dB)
Strip	Doldrums	1803339	-15.1
		1817737	-9.2
		1839745	-14.2
		1839746	-12.5
		1839747	-10.8
	Desert	1801689	-15.9
		1801819	-13.6
Spot	Doldrums	1801594	-16.1
		1801595	-13.2
		1801596	-13.9
		1801597	-13.9
		1801598	-14.3
	Desert	1803341	-13.0
		1803342	-15.8

Table 9. NESZ of the X12 scenes for the Atlantic Doldrums and Sahara Desert.

Imaging mode	Area	Image ID	NESZ (dB)
Strip	Doldrums	1801642	-17.9
		1805280	-15.0
		1805281	-12.6
		1839748	-10.0

Spot	Desert	1839749	-9.6
		1801690	-16.4
		1801691	-16.2
	Doldrums	1801599	-13.8
		1801600	-14.0
		1801601	-12.6
		1801602	-13.0
		1801603	-13.5
	Desert	1801740	-13.8
1821541		-13.9	

Table 10. NESZ of the X13 scenes for the Atlantic Doldrums and Sahara Desert.

Imaging mode	Area	Image ID	NESZ (dB)
Strip	Doldrums	1805463	-16.7
		1805464	-14.9
		1813155	-16.1
		1816892	-15.2
		1817738	-10.0
	Desert	1801692	-16.2
1801820		-13.8	
Spot	Doldrums	1801604	-15.9
		1801605	-13.8
		1801606	-13.8
		1801607	-14.1
		1801608	-13.2
	Desert	1801741	-14.1
		1801742	-13.2

The measured NESZ values are mostly higher than the values provided by ICEYE. For X11 only one, for X12 none, and for X13 two of the analysed scenes have NESZ in line with the values stated in the ICEYE documentation. The measured strong NESZ is partly caused by an overestimation due to the method used in the SQT. When calculating the σ^0 range profiles, all pixels in the azimuth direction are averaged, rather than choosing only the low backscatter pixels in the averaging. In contrary, the methodology used by ICEYE for calculating the NESZ ignores the higher backscatter pixels of the sample and therefore the calculated NESZ is lower. The methodology applied by ICEYE is documented in RD-6. Another possible reason for the relatively high observed NESZ in some of the images is the difficulty in finding areas with very low backscatter. This is because the analysis is performed on co-polarization data and not on cross-polarization, the shallowest possible incidence angle offered by ICEYE is only 30° for Strip and 35° for Spot, and the imaged surfaces are often not ideally flat. Even though the images were collected from the Doldrums zone, some winds can still be present in the imaged areas causing small waves which increase the observed backscatter. The selected relatively smooth desert surfaces may also contain some wavy terrain or rocks and thus reflect back some of the SAR signal.

3.5 Radiometric Stability

The radiometric stability and consistency reflect the ability of the satellite measurements to repeatedly produce similar calibrated backscatter values from targets having the same properties and conditions. Better radiometric stability thus enables the users to correctly analyse and interpret multiple observations acquired at different times or from different locations having the same target properties.

3.5.1 Method

The radiometric stability of SAR is usually tested over rainforests, because they result in a spatially homogeneous backscatter with small seasonal changes and low dependency on incidence angle. For assessing the radiometric stability, all acquired data from the Amazonas Rainforest are analysed. Radiometric range profiles calculated with σ^0 as output at five representative points along the azimuth direction (as in the AEP analysis, Figure 4). An average of all samples was calculated for each SAR scene using the linear power units, and the result was converted to decibel values. The standard deviation was calculated directly from the decibel values.

3.5.2 Results Compliance

The absolute radiometric accuracy (within one data scene and over time) derived during the commissioning phases by ICEYE was 2 dB RMSE (RD-9). The relative radiometric accuracy, indicating the standard deviation of the observations within one data scene is defined as 1 dB.

The average and the standard deviation for each analysed scene are presented in Table 11. The colours of the cells indicate the level of consistency in relation to the most typical observed value of approximately -6 dB for the Spot data and -5.5 dB for the Strip data. The green colour indicates good radiometric stability, with a deviation less than 0.5 dB from the most typical value. The light green refers to moderate radiometric stability with deviations of 0.5-1.5 dB, and the yellow colour to relatively poor stability with a deviation larger than 1.5 dB from the most typical backscatter value.

Generally, the radiometric stability of the ICEYE data can be considered good, with a backscatter variation usually less than 0.5 dB from the most typical backscatter level. The stability is somewhat better for the Spot data compared to the Strip data, maybe due to the smaller variation in the antenna elevation range (see section 3.3). If comparing these results with the ones derived in the previous analysis of ICEYE X4-X7 satellites, a significant improvement in the radiometric stability compared to the older generation can be seen.

Table 11: Radiometric stability of the ICEYE satellites over the Amazonas Rainforest. The average and the standard deviation in decibels for each scene is listed. Green, light green and yellow cell colors indicate a deviation of up to 0.5 dB, up to 1.5 dB, and more than 1.5 dB, respectively, from the typical backscatter of -6.0 dB for Spot and -5.5 dB for Strip.

Imaging mode	X11	X12	X13
Spot	-6.33 ± 0.78	-6.64 ± 0.87	-6.15 ± 0.45
	-6.17 ± 0.65	-5.96 ± 0.55	-5.70 ± 0.23
	-6.36 ± 0.66	-6.48 ± 0.63	-6.40 ± 0.71
	-5.98 ± 0.70	-6.05 ± 0.67	-4.84 ± 0.68
	-5.93 ± 0.92	-6.64 ± 0.63	-5.27 ± 0.66
	-5.60 ± 0.84	-5.30 ± 0.81	-6.93 ± 0.50
Strip	-4.59 ± 0.42	-5.68 ± 0.48	-4.74 ± 0.51
	-5.51 ± 0.51	-5.52 ± 0.47	-5.41 ± 0.51
	-6.34 ± 0.56	-4.62 ± 0.41	-5.07 ± 0.38
	-5.56 ± 0.75	-5.11 ± 0.44	-5.04 ± 0.44
	-4.47 ± 0.37	-6.35 ± 0.58	-4.91 ± 0.47
	-5.02 ± 0.76	-6.54 ± 0.64	-7.17 ± 0.64

4. DETAILED VALIDATION – GEOMETRIC

This chapter describes the validation of the IRF quality parameters performed by the EDAP+ team over the point target sites, using test datasets of the X11, X12 and X13 satellites. The IRF-analysis includes the assessment of the spatial resolution, side lobes and geolocation accuracy.

4.1 Introduction

IRF analyses are performed over dedicated sites with installed trihedral corner reflectors (CRs), providing quality values for spatial resolution, geolocation accuracy, and the power distribution of the measured radar beam (PSLR and ISLR). Suitable CR sites for the IRF analyses were selected based on the orbits and coverage of the individual satellites. In order to reduce the overall time needed for the collection of all required test data, three different CR sites were selected for the IRF analysis:

- Rosamond in California, US, managed by JPL:
<https://uavsar.jpl.nasa.gov/cgi-bin/calibration.pl> (accessed 07/2023)
- Neustrelitz in Germany, managed by the German Aerospace Center (DLR):
<https://calvalportal.ceos.org/neustrelitz-germany> (accessed 07/2023)
- Surat Basin in Queensland, Australia, managed by Geoscience Australia [RD-10].

The Rosamond site contains several trihedral CRs with face widths of 4.8 m, 2.4 m, and 0.7 m (Figure 13). All large (4.8 m) and small (0.7 m) reflectors are directed towards east, and approximately half of the medium size (2.4 m) are directed towards east and half towards west. In Rosamond, all possible overpassing orbits were thus accepted, namely both right and left looking acquisitions of the ascending and descending orbits.

Figure 13: A Google Earth view of the Rosamond CR site in California. The smaller image in the upper right side shows the surrounding area of the site. The bottom

image is a closer view on the CR site, showing the CR names, alignment, and distribution at the site.

The Surat Basin CR test area is located in Queensland, Australia, spreading over an area of approximately 130 x 130 km. A total of 42 dihedral CRs with a face size of 1.5 m are distributed at the site, with a typical distance of ~15 km between reflectors. All CRs at the site are facing towards west, and therefore only ascending right looking and descending left looking orbits were selected. The site is less suitable for the analysis of Spot acquisitions, because one scene of 5 x 5 km usually covers only one CR. For the Strip data with a scene size of 30 x 50 km, one acquisition typically covers about 5 CRs. Therefore, only Strip data were collected over the Surat Basin site. Figure 14 shows the CRs of Surat Basin with yellow pins over a Google Earth view.

Figure 14: A Google Earth view of the Surat Basin CR area in Queensland, Australia. The yellow pins show the location of the CRs.

The Neustrelitz site contains 4 trihedral CRs with a face width of 1.5 m (Figure 15). Three of the reflectors; D33, D35 and D36, are directed towards west and one (D34) towards east. Hence, only ascending right looking and descending left looking orbits were selected. Strip acquisitions were preferred over Rosamond and Surat Basin, because in these sites one scene covers a larger number of CRs compared to the Neustrelitz site. Only Spot data was thus collected from the Neustrelitz site. The coordinates and elevation of the Neustrelitz CR are presented in Table 12.

Table 12: Coordinates of the Neustrelitz corner reflectors.

CR name	Latitude (decimal degrees)	Longitude (decimal degrees)	Elevation (m.a.s.l.)
D33	53.32945	13.06939	67
D34	53.33008	13.06963	70
D35	53.33020	13.06952	70
D36	53.32938	13.06991	65

Figure 15: A Google Earth view of the Neustrelitz CR site in Germany. The small image in the upper right side shows the surrounding area of the CR site. The large image is a closer view, showing the CR names and distribution at the site.

As in the radiometric analysis presented in Chapter 3, also in the IRF-analysis, the SAR Quality Toolbox (SQT) is used for assessing the quality metrics, and the measured quality values are compared with the corresponding values provided in the ICEYE documentation. Table 13, Table 14 and Table 15 show details on the ICEYE data acquisitions used in the IRF analysis of the X11, X12 and X13 satellites, respectively.

Table 13: X11 data products included in the assessment of the IRF quality parameters, provided by ICEYE to the EDAP+ team.

Test area	Im. mode	ID number	Date	Orbit	Look direction	Inc. angle	Proc. version
Rosamond, California	Strip	1870510	2023-02-12	Asc	Left	17.7	1.80
		1932564	2023-03-05	Desc	Left	23.4	1.82
		1932565	2023-03-06	Desc	Right	25.7	1.83
		1949514	2023-03-10	Desc	Left	21.8	1.88
		1953792	2023-03-11	Desc	Right	27.8	1.90
		1984225	2023-03-24	Asc	Left	15.6	1.88
	2008073	2023-03-28	Asc	Right	25.0	1.86	
	Spot	1821030	2023-01-26	Asc	Right	26.9	1.80
		1835027	2023-02-03	Desc	Right	25.9	1.80
		1835029	2023-02-07	Asc	Left	29.5	1.80
		1835030	2023-02-07	Desc	Left	32.5	1.80
		1864740	2023-02-11	Asc	Right	28.9	1.80
1872611		2023-02-19	Desc	Right	34.2	1.80	
Neustrelitz, Germany	Spot	1821033	2023-01-30	Asc	Right	28.2	1.80
		1872603	2023-02-20	Asc	Right	31.5	1.80
		1881654	2023-02-15	Asc	Right	26.4	1.80
Surat Basin, Australia	Strip	1870509	2023-02-12	Desc	Left	26.6	1.80
		1870513	2023-02-17	Desc	Left	27.2	1.80

Table 14: X12 data products included in the assessment of the IRF quality parameters, provided by ICEYE to the EDAP+ team.

Test area	Im. mode	ID number	Date	Orbit	Look direction	Inc. angle	Proc. version
Rosamond, California	Strip	1874306	2023-02-12	Asc	Right	15.3	1.80
		1874381	2023-02-13	Asc	Left	15.4	1.80
		1877717	2023-02-14	Desc	Left	26.6	1.80
		1888273	2023-02-21	Asc	Left	17.6	1.80
		1894926	2023-02-22	Desc	Left	23.4	1.80
		1907856	2023-03-01	Asc	Left	24.3	1.82
	Spot	1821029	2023-01-26	Asc	Right	30.6	1.80
		1821031	2023-01-28	Asc	Left	24.9	1.80
		1835604	2023-02-06	Desc	Left	24.0	1.80
		1883416	2023-02-16	Desc	Right	31.6	1.80
Neustrelitz, Germany	Spot	1839364	2023-02-01	Asc	Right	29.6	1.80
		1883417	2023-02-17	Asc	Right	33.4	1.90
		1898700	2023-02-25	Asc	Right	30.8	1.82
		1923872	2023-03-03	Desc	Left	29.8	1.82
		1928906	2023-03-05	Asc	Right	24.7	1.82
Surat Basin, Australia	Strip	1874380	2023-02-13	Desc	Left	24.1	1.80
		1888272	2023-02-21	Desc	Left	22.0	1.80
		1925319	2023-03-04	Asc	Right	21.4	1.82

Table 15: X13 data products included in the assessment of the IRF quality parameters, provided by ICEYE to the EDAP+ team.

Test area	Im. mode	ID number	Date	Orbit	Look direction	Inc. angle	Proc. version
Rosamond, California	Strip	1859213	2023-02-09	Desc	Right	27.4	1.80
		1870050	2023-02-15	Desc	Left	23.5	1.80
		1870075	2023-02-14	Asc	Left	16.6	1.80
		1899652	2023-02-24	Desc	Right	25.6	1.82
		1908302	2023-03-01	Asc	Left	20.2	1.82
		1923875	2023-03-02	Desc	Left	17.8	1.82
	Spot	1821032	2023-01-28	Asc	Right	27.0	1.80
		1821034	2023-01-30	Asc	Left	31.1	1.80
		1835025	2023-02-01	Desc	Right	21.9	1.80
		1835028	2023-02-05	Asc	Right	24.0	1.80
		1859149	2023-02-07	Desc	Left	32.1	1.80
		1896053	2023-02-22	Asc	Left	30.1	1.80
		Neustrelitz, Germany	Spot	1821028	2023-01-26	Asc	Right
1835026	2023-02-03			Asc	Right	21.9	1.80
1876905	2023-02-18			Asc	Right	29.5	1.80
Surat Basin, Australia	Strip	1865121	2023-02-10	Asc	Right	17.5	1.80
		1870074	2023-02-14	Desc	Left	23.8	1.82
		1899653	2023-02-25	Asc	Right	18.6	1.82

4.2 Spatial Resolution and Side Lobes

The spatial resolution and the strength of the side lobes with respect to the main lobe determine the ability of the SAR data to distinguish objects on the image. The spatial resolution is defined as the width of the main lobe in range and azimuth at a level of 3 dB below the maximum of the main lobe, as marked by the red dashed horizontal lines in Figure 17. The peak side lobe ratio (PSLR) represents the relation between the closest side lobes (to the main lobe) and the main lobe, while the integrated side lobe (ISLR) the relation between all relevant side lobes and the main lobe. Hence, the narrower is the main lobe and the smaller are the side lobes, the better is the ability of the SAR data to distinguish smaller objects in the image from the surrounding area.

4.2.1 Method

The distribution of the measured power from the reflectors and the area around the reflectors are analysed, providing the spatial resolution of the SAR data and the power of the secondary lobes relative to the main lobe (PSLR and ISLR). The individual CRs are first located automatically by the SQT or by manually selecting specific CRs, and the IRF parameters are then calculated by the software for the included CRs. A screenshot showing an example of the IRF analysis in the SQT for Neustrelitz is shown in Figure 16. The bright points in the image are the reflectors as observed by the SAR scene. Figure 17 shows an example of the spatial distribution of the measured power from one of the CRs in Rosamond and the obtained results for the spatial resolution, PSLR and ISLR.

Figure 16: IRF analysis of Scene 1883417 over Neustrelitz, Germany, using the SQT. Corner reflectors installed at the site are visible in the SAR image, next to the red points.

Figure 17: Assessment of the spatial resolution, PSLR and ISLR with the SQT. An example showing the main and the side lobes for the Spot scene 1835604 acquired with the X12 satellite over Rosamond.

4.2.2 Results Compliance

Table 20 shows the quality values related to the spatial resolution and the side lobes provided in the ICEYE online interactive product documentation (checked 06/2023). The range spatial resolution is given in slant range direction for the assessed SLC data. The spatial resolution is given for each imaging mode separately. A single quality value of the PSLR and localization uncertainty is provided by ICEYE for all imaging modes. A value for the ISLR is not currently provided by ICEYE in the public documentation. In an old version of the Product Guide an ISLR of approximately -4.4 dB was defined by ICEYE, but in the more recent analyses performed by ICEYE for the X11-X13 satellites, the measured ISLR was mostly between -12 and -9 dB. Therefore, the reference ISLR concerning the EDAP+ evaluation activity is defined in Table 20 as between -12 and -4.4 dB.

Table 16: Quality values related to the IRF analysis, provided in the ICEYE documentation.

Product type	Range resolution [m]	Azimuth resolution [m]	PSLR [dB]	ISLR [dB]	Loc. error RMSE [m]
Strip	0.5...2.5	3	-13.3	-12...-4.4	6
Spot	0.5	0.25			

Table 17, Table 18 and Table 19 show the results of the measured spatial resolution, PSLR and ISLR for the analysed satellites X11, X12 and X13, respectively. The spatial resolution in range and azimuth directions was nearly always better or in line with the values provided in the ICEYE documentation, with values of 0.5-1.0 m in range and 2.1-2.8 m in azimuth for Strip, and values usually close to 0.46 m in range and 0.23 m in azimuth for Spot. There were only few exceptions

of Spot scenes with somewhat coarser spatial resolution than the values provided in ICEYE's documentation.

The measured PSLR and ISLR were usually around the values provided in the ICEYE documentation or in ICEYE's own validation for X11-X13 [RD-6]. Both the range and the azimuth PLSR was typically between -15 and -12 dB, with some exceptions showing smaller or larger values. The ISLR in azimuth and range directions was typically between -12 and -9, which is significantly smaller than the value of -4.4 provided in the old version of the Product Guide, but very similar to the values ICEYE have received for X11-X13 satellites in their own validation activities.

It should be noted that compared to other available spaceborne X-band SAR data, the spatial resolution of the ICEYE products is very good, while the side lobes are relatively strong. This is because in the product processing, a windowing function is not applied. A windowing function, such as Taylor, Hanning, Hamming or Kaiser, which is often applied in SAR processing, reduces the side lobes while also reducing the spatial resolution of the data. Generally, based on our assessment described above, the spatial resolution of the ICEYE X11-X13 data can be considered very good, and the side lobes can be considered good.

Table 17: IRF spatial resolution and side lobes for X11.

Area	Im. mode	Im. ID	Resolution (Rg) [m]	Resolution (Az) [m]	PSLR (Rg) [dB]	PSLR (Az) [dB]	ISLR (Rg) [dB]	ISLR (Az) [dB]
Strip	Rosamond	1870510	0.5 ± 0.02	2.34 ± 0.1	-12.62 ± 2.3	-14.37 ± 2.09	-9.3 ± 2.55	-11.16 ± 3.01
		1932564	0.8 ± 0.01	2.3 ± 0.02	-12.75 ± 0.64	-14.97 ± 0.78	-9.79 ± 0.72	-11.77 ± 0.9
		1932565	0.87 ± 0.01	2.22 ± 0.03	-12.82 ± 0.73	-15.05 ± 0.84	-9.7 ± 1.03	-12.02 ± 1.16
		1949514	0.75 ± 0	2.75 ± 0.02	-13.13 ± 0.42	-14 ± 0.83	-9.86 ± 0.39	-11.62 ± 0.43
		1953792	0.97 ± 0	2.73 ± 0.01	-13.19 ± 0.15	-14.31 ± 0.37	-10.22 ± 0.16	-11.72 ± 0.28
		1984225	0.52 ± 0.02	2.74 ± 0.02	-13.2 ± 0.95	-13.95 ± 0.74	-9.61 ± 0.95	-11.34 ± 0.72
	2008073	0.86 ± 0.01	2.75 ± 0.04	-13.34 ± 0.39	-14.35 ± 0.3	-10.19 ± 0.15	-11.78 ± 0.17	
	Surat Basin	1870509	0.9 ± 0	2.29 ± 0.01	-13.31 ± 0.08	-15.03 ± 0.11	-10.35 ± 0.06	-12.34 ± 0.15
	1870513	0.93 ± 0	2.29 ± 0.01	-13.29 ± 0.22	-14.97 ± 0.09	-10.28 ± 0.17	-12.34 ± 0.08	
Spot	Rosamond	1821030	0.46 ± 0.01	0.23 ± 0.02	-12.98 ± 1.11	-11.83 ± 2.96	-9.83 ± 1.9	-8.91 ± 3.05
		1835027	0.46 ± 0.01	0.22 ± 0	-13.37 ± 0.47	-12.33 ± 1.14	-10.49 ± 0.22	-9.69 ± 1.12
		1835029	0.46 ± 0.03	0.26 ± 0.07	-10.85 ± 3.84	-12.09 ± 3.59	-8.2 ± 4.16	-9.56 ± 5.89
		1835030	0.46 ± 0.03	0.2 ± 0.03	-14.88 ± 7.97	-11.06 ± 3.26	-13.05 ± 9.03	-8.56 ± 4.5
		1864740	0.45 ± 0.01	0.23 ± 0.03	-13.29 ± 0.84	-13.5 ± 3.13	-10.51 ± 0.5	-10.62 ± 2.81
		1872611	0.53 ± 0.24	0.23 ± 0.07	-13.03 ± 0.51	-12.69 ± 0.82	-10.25 ± 0.68	-9.99 ± 1
	Neustre litz	1821033	0.45 ± 0	0.21 ± 0	-13.32 ± 0.05	-13.03 ± 0.05	-10.61 ± 0.01	-10.19 ± 0.06
		1872603	0.45 ± 0	0.22 ± 0	-13.1 ± 0.07	-12.86 ± 0.03	-10.52 ± 0.02	-10.21 ± 0.03
		1881654	0.45 ± 0	0.22 ± 0	-13.16 ± 0.01	-12.93 ± 0.15	-10.55 ± 0.02	-10.24 ± 0.04

Table 18: IRF spatial resolution and side lobes for X12.

Area	Im. mode	Im. ID	Resolution (Rg) [m]	Resolution (Az) [m]	PSLR (Rg) [dB]	PSLR (Az) [dB]	ISLR (Rg) [dB]	ISLR (Az) [dB]
Strip	Rosamond	1874306	0.5 ± 0.02	2.4 ± 0.24	-13.44 ± 0.76	-15.55 ± 2.15	-9.94 ± 1.08	-12.5 ± 1.93
		1874381	0.51 ± 0.01	2.29 ± 0.01	-13.67 ± 0.71	-14.84 ± 0.54	-10.31 ± 0.73	-12.09 ± 0.64
		1877717	0.91 ± 0.01	2.34 ± 0.07	-12.95 ± 0.94	-13.72 ± 1.2	-9.52 ± 1.5	-10.62 ± 2.3
		1888273	0.6 ± 0.02	2.09 ± 0.01	-13.6 ± 0.31	-15.44 ± 0.29	-10.4 ± 0.24	-12.82 ± 0.18
		1894926	0.81 ± 0	2.15 ± 0.03	-13.06 ± 0.4	-14.58 ± 1.29	-10.07 ± 0.46	-11.86 ± 1.46
		1907856	0.84 ± 0.01	2.27 ± 0.01	-13.04 ± 0.49	-15.03 ± 0.37	-10.15 ± 0.36	-12.38 ± 0.33

	Surat Basin	1874380	0.83 ± 0	2.75 ± 0.01	-13.13 ± 0.14	-14.41 ± 0.25	-10.33 ± 0.11	-11.69 ± 0.2
		1888272	0.75 ± 0	2.16 ± 0.01	-13.23 ± 0.07	-15.24 ± 0.62	-10.4 ± 0.11	-12.57 ± 0.43
		1925319	0.74 ± 0	2.15 ± 0.01	-13.23 ± 0.01	-15.55 ± 0.07	-10.42 ± 0.08	-12.84 ± 0.13
Spot	Rosamond	1821029	0.46 ± 0.01	0.24 ± 0.04	-13.42 ± 1.06	-11.25 ± 3.38	-10.04 ± 2.03	-8.54 ± 3.11
		1821031	0.46 ± 0	0.22 ± 0.01	-13.63 ± 0.54	-12.76 ± 0.94	-10.72 ± 0.31	-9.98 ± 1.16
		1835604	0.46 ± 0.02	0.22 ± 0.01	-13.64 ± 0.89	-11.02 ± 2.89	-10.18 ± 0.98	-8.18 ± 2.87
		1883416	0.46 ± 0	0.22 ± 0	-13.77 ± 0.11	-12.85 ± 0.9	-10.76 ± 0.06	-10.12 ± 0.49
	Neustrelitz	1839364	0.46 ± 0	0.22 ± 0	-13.79 ± 0.07	-13.11 ± 0.06	-10.89 ± 0.06	-10.22 ± 0.03
		1883417	0.46 ± 0	0.22 ± 0	-13.75 ± 0.09	-12.36 ± 0.09	-10.88 ± 0.04	-10.17 ± 0.02
		1898700	0.46 ± 0	0.22 ± 0	-13.76 ± 0.04	-12.89 ± 0.15	-10.87 ± 0.04	-10.18 ± 0.01
		1923872	0.62 ± 0.13	0.22 ± 0	-13.67 ± 0.02	-12.96 ± 0.62	-10.7 ± 0.05	-11.03 ± 0.48
		1928906	0.46 ± 0	0.22 ± 0.01	-13.73 ± 0.03	-12.62 ± 0.09	-10.86 ± 0.01	-10.23 ± 0.01

Table 19: IRF spatial resolution and side lobes for X13.

Area	Im. mode	Im. ID	Resolution (Rg) [m]	Resolution (Az) [m]	PSLR (Rg) [dB]	PSLR (Az) [dB]	ISLR (Rg) [dB]	ISLR (Az) [dB]
Strip	Rosamond	1859213	0.93 ± 0.01	2.31 ± 0.01	-12.68 ± 0.6	-14.49 ± 1.04	-9.73 ± 1.42	-11.38 ± 1.79
		1870050	0.81 ± 0.01	2.26 ± 0.05	-13.06 ± 0.27	-14.6 ± 1.25	-9.69 ± 1.3	-11.38 ± 2.04
		1870075	0.56 ± 0.01	2.29 ± 0.01	-13.37 ± 0.41	-14.84 ± 0.56	-10.22 ± 0.55	-12.07 ± 0.48
		1899652	0.88 ± 0	2.73 ± 0.01	-12.94 ± 0.24	-14.2 ± 0.34	-10.22 ± 0.17	-11.56 ± 0.26
		1908302	0.68 ± 0.01	2.1 ± 0.04	-13.24 ± 0.69	-15.42 ± 0.77	-10.04 ± 1.23	-12.45 ± 0.51
		1923875	0.6 ± 0	2.73 ± 0.01	-13.05 ± 0.39	-14.3 ± 0.3	-10.02 ± 0.43	-11.43 ± 0.42
	Surat Basin	1865121	0.59 ± 0	2.11 ± 0.01	-13.42 ± 0.16	-15.3 ± 0.3	-10.48 ± 0.11	-12.69 ± 0.22
		1870074	0.83 ± 0	2.28 ± 0.01	-13.66 ± 0.16	-14.74 ± 0.54	-11.27 ± 0.16	-12.04 ± 0.4
		1899653	0.63 ± 0	2.32 ± 0.01	-13.44 ± 0.24	-14.98 ± 0.26	-10.48 ± 0.12	-12.23 ± 0.19
Spot	Rosamond	1821032	0.46 ± 0	0.22 ± 0.02	-13.4 ± 0.87	-12.05 ± 2.35	-10.19 ± 1.56	-9.39 ± 2.34
		1821034	0.46 ± 0	0.23 ± 0.01	-13.48 ± 0.16	-12.89 ± 0.3	-10.62 ± 0.14	-10.23 ± 0.19
		1835025	0.45 ± 0	0.22 ± 0	-13.47 ± 0.12	-12.95 ± 0.25	-10.6 ± 0.08	-10.09 ± 0.42
		1835028	0.46 ± 0.02	0.22 ± 0.03	-13.56 ± 0.88	-10.75 ± 3.85	-10.32 ± 0.8	-7.9 ± 4.19
		1859149	0.53 ± 0.09	0.25 ± 0.04	-16.49 ± 6.93	-9.56 ± 4.22	-18.75 ± 17.27	-8.95 ± 5.71
		1896053	0.52 ± 0.16	0.24 ± 0.03	-13.87 ± 0.94	-12.39 ± 3.18	-11.06 ± 0.51	-10.31 ± 1.34
	Neustrelitz	1821028	0.45 ± 0	0.22 ± 0	-13.56 ± 0.04	-13.11 ± 0.08	-10.76 ± 0.03	-10.32 ± 0.02
		1835026	0.46 ± 0.01	0.22 ± 0	-13.54 ± 0.03	-12.97 ± 0.21	-10.69 ± 0.04	-10.16 ± 0.12
		1876905	0.46 ± 0	0.22 ± 0	-13.49 ± 0.1	-12.62 ± 0.48	-10.71 ± 0.06	-10.18 ± 0.06

4.3 Geolocation Accuracy

4.3.1 Method

The IRF analysis typically includes a calculation of the localization error of a SAR scene. The given locations of bright targets (CRs) are compared with the locations of the CRs in the SAR image. The localization error is expressed in both azimuth and range directions. Figure 18 presents an example of localization accuracy analysis for one CR over Rosamond, for the Spot scene 1835604 acquired over Rosamond with the X12 satellite. The red dot is the expected location of the reflector on the SAR image, based on the geographical coordinates of the reflector (e.g. the true location). The

green plus (+) sign shows the location of the same reflector on the SAR image, detected by the software based on the backscatter distribution.

Figure 18. Geolocation accuracy assessment with the SQT. The expected point target (red dot) location is compared with the location on the observed SAR image (green plus sign). The example above is from the Spot scene 1835604 acquired with the X12 satellite over Rosamond.

4.3.2 Results Compliance

Table 20 shows the quality values related to the localization error provided in the ICEYE online interactive product documentation (checked 06/2023), and in the additional documentation received from ICEYE [RD-6]. The RMSE of the localization error provided by ICEYE is 6 m, while the CE90 localization error is 9 m, both values are the same for the Strip and Spot imaging modes. In our analysis we calculated the localization errors in slant range. Concerning the relatively steep incidence angles of the ICEYE data, the localization errors in ground range are notably larger than the errors in slant range. For 15° and 35° incidence angles, the localization errors in ground range would be 3.9 and 1.7 times larger than the errors in slant range, respectively. It is unclear in the ICEYE documentation whether the 6 m RMSE and 9 m CE90 relate to the error in slant or ground range. Hence, we considered both options in our assessment.

Table 20: Quality values of the test dataset related to the IRF analysis, provided in the ICEYE documentation.

Product type	Localization error RMSE	Localization error CE90
Strip	6 m	9 m
Spot		

Several received products had large localization errors of over 20 m either in azimuth or range direction. After a request by the EDAP+ team, these data were inspected and reprocessed by ICEYE, which usually improved their localization accuracy. Table 21, Table 22 and Table 23 show the results of the localization error analysis performed over the CR sites for satellites X11, X12 and

X13, respectively. The range error is provided in slant range, and the ALE (absolute localization error) is the circular error calculated from the errors in azimuth and slant range. Concerning the reprocessed scenes, the tables present the localization errors of the corrected products. For the X12's Spot scene 1883417 from Neustrelitz, the geolocation accuracy could not be properly calculated, most likely due a large geolocation shift.

Table 21: IRF localization accuracy for X11.

Im. mode	Area	Im. ID	Range error [m]	Azimuth error [m]	ALE
Strip	Rosamond	1870510	4.06 ± 0.67	-6.07 ± 2.2	7.30
		1932564	-3.52 ± 1.05	2.62 ± 2.87	4.39
		1932565	-6.04 ± 0.83	-3.29 ± 0.56	6.88
		1949514	-3.83 ± 0.77	4.33 ± 0.69	5.78
		1953792	3.3 ± 0.9	-0.66 ± 0.55	3.37
		1984225	-6.28 ± 0.38	7.99 ± 0.22	10.16
	2008073	0.58 ± 1.54	10.26 ± 2.54	10.28	
	Surat Basin	1870509	-7.45 ± 0.24	0.21 ± 0.26	7.45
		1870513	8.57 ± 0.27	6.61 ± 0.93	10.82
Spot	Rosamond	1821030	-6.3 ± 0.82	1.45 ± 0.33	6.46
		1835027	-2.82 ± 0.84	-2.04 ± 0.35	3.48
		1835029	3.91 ± 4.39	2.26 ± 1.13	4.52
		1835030	1.36 ± 1.45	2.07 ± 1.71	2.48
		1864740	-5.5 ± 1	2.02 ± 0.29	5.86
		1872611	1.07 ± 0.85	-2.68 ± 0.14	2.89
	Neustrelitz	1821033	-6.57 ± 0.19	1.72 ± 0.13	6.79
		1872603	4.1 ± 0.24	5.79 ± 0.12	7.09
		1881654	-0.46 ± 0.26	5.37 ± 0.12	5.39

Table 22: IRF localization accuracy for X12.

Im. mode	Area	Im. ID	Range error [m]	Azimuth error [m]	ALE
Strip	Rosamond	1874306	3.73 ± 0.43	-6.41 ± 0.36	7.42
		1874381	1.39 ± 0.41	-3.36 ± 0.18	3.64
		1877717	-2.03 ± 0.77	2 ± 0.64	2.85
		1888273	2.66 ± 0.61	-6.24 ± 0.24	6.78
		1894926	-1.59 ± 1.06	2.01 ± 2.89	2.56
		1907856	7.5 ± 0.62	-1.75 ± 0.2	7.70
	Surat Basin	1874380	-0.17 ± 0.07	1.59 ± 0.35	1.60
		1888272	-2.59 ± 0.13	2.83 ± 0.27	3.84
		1925319	0.79 ± 0.04	2.05 ± 0.1	2.20
Spot	Rosamond	1821029	-6.16 ± 0.94	0.02 ± 0.33	6.16
		1821031	6.5 ± 0.6	1.59 ± 0.2	6.69
		1835604	0.07 ± 1.13	1.85 ± 0.78	1.85
		1883416	2.87 ± 2.15	8.14 ± 0.63	8.63
	Neustrelitz	1839364	-5.84 ± 0.25	-0.03 ± 0.12	5.84
		1883417			
		1898700	-5.28 ± 0.25	1.36 ± 0.12	5.45
		1923872	-2.37 ± 0.25	2.71 ± 0.14	3.60
1928906	-6.42 ± 0.47	-1.86 ± 0.12	6.68		

Table 23: IRF localization accuracy for X13.

Im. mode	Area	Im. ID	Range error [m]	Azimuth error [m]	ALE
Strip	Rosamond	1859213	-1.58 ± 0.04	1.8 ± 0.09	2.40
		1870050	-4.15 ± 1.02	8.21 ± 2.86	9.20
		1870075	6.11 ± 0.43	0.17 ± 0.2	6.11
		1899652	-0.42 ± 0.59	1.25 ± 0.4	1.32
		1908302	7.29 ± 0.53	-0.79 ± 0.19	7.33
		1923875	-0.63 ± 0.9	6.35 ± 0.83	6.38
	Surat Basin	1865121	4 ± 0.08	2.02 ± 0.13	4.48
		1870074	-6.12 ± 0.31	0.39 ± 1.04	6.13
		1899653	1.48 ± 0.06	1.65 ± 0.15	2.22
Spot	Rosamond	1821032	-4.7 ± 1	2.42 ± 0.32	5.29
		1821034	6.02 ± 0.54	1.88 ± 0.26	6.31
		1835025	-2.41 ± 0.72	1.94 ± 0.58	3.09
		1835028	-2.95 ± 0.94	2.52 ± 0.48	3.88
		1859149	1.11 ± 2.45	1.9 ± 1.76	2.20
		1896053	6.19 ± 0.73	2.28 ± 1.56	6.60
	Neustrelitz	1821028	-6.58 ± 0.14	0.53 ± 0.12	6.60
		1835026	-4.06 ± 0.28	2.83 ± 0.1	4.95
		1876905	2.03 ± 0.25	8.88 ± 0.12	9.11

The localization errors presented in Table 21, Table 22, Table 23 were usually close to or smaller than the value specified by ICEYE. The average absolute errors in slant range and azimuth calculated from all three satellites were 3.4 m and 2.7 m, respectively, and the ALE was on average 4.8 m. However, the measured errors in slant range projected to the ground range would result in localization errors usually larger than the 6 m RMSE stated by ICEYE.

Hence, overall, concerning the errors in slant range and in azimuth, the geolocation accuracy of the data can be considered in line with the ICEYE documentation, but in ground range the errors would be larger than the provided values. This applies to the products after the corrections and reprocessing was applied by ICEYE. In case the geolocation accuracy assessment would have been performed only on the data scenes delivered for the first time, also the geolocation errors in slant range and azimuth would have been generally larger than the stated values in the ICEYE documentation, and sometimes with quite large localization errors of over 20 m.